

Data Management Plan for Master's Thesis Writers

Thesis topic/title:

Thesis author:

1. Describe the research data of your thesis briefly into the table below:		
1. What kind of research data do you have? Survey, interview, observation, measurements, pictures, videos, samples etc.	2. Where does your research data originate from? Do you produce/collect your own data? Are you utilising pre-existing data, e.g. from a research group or a register?	3. What is the file format of your research data? e.g. jpg (picture)/ .docx (word)/ .csv (excel)/ .sav (SPSS) / .mp3 (audio) Note! It is possible to have multiple file formats.

2. How do you document the data you have collected/utilised? Think about the information that you would need in order to interpret and re-use of your data even after years have passed.

3. What are the specific points to note about your data? Do you, for example, process personal data?

4. Where do you storage your data during your studies? How do you back up your data?

5. What do you do with the data after your thesis is finished and you have graduated?